

Iodine Promoted Thermal Synthesis of Carbazole from Aniline*

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Aniline under iodine promoted thermal reaction has been found to yield carbazole, diphenylamine and other products. Their formation has been discussed in the light of results obtained by peroxidase and anodic oxidation of aniline or related compounds.

RECENTLY the cyclisation of diphenylamine to carbazole has been effected by photolytic and anodic oxidation methods in addition to various other methods previously described¹⁻⁴. Carruthers⁵ synthesised glycozoline using photolytic methods which primarily involved hydrogen abstraction and subsequent cyclisation. In the anodic oxidation method the formation of cyclic *trans* dihydrocarbazole and subsequent dehydrogenation has been postulated. Greabe and Glaser⁶ obtained carbazole from diphenylamine and aniline at red heat temperature. Recently Mullineax⁷ and Raley using I₂ as dehydrogenating agent reported that various acyclic compounds formed unsaturated and aromatic hydrocarbons at 400-500°. The radical iodine(I) formed at high temperature was considered to be the hydrogen abstracting species. Hydrogen abstracting reaction using I₂ as a catalyst used by us⁸ to effect the conversion of diphenylamine to carbazole in sealed tube at 350°.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The alumina used was of Brockmann grade as prepared by Sarabhai Merck Co. of India.

Freshly distilled aniline (1.5 g) was heated at 350° in a sealed tube for about 3 hours with a trace of iodine. After completion of the reaction the sealed tube was broken and poured into water. Smell of ammonia was perceived and from the water soluble portion of the reaction mixture it was again detected by the action of alkali and Nessler's reagent. Water insoluble part was fractionated into basic and neutral fractions. Each fractions were chromatographed separately over alumina. The residue obtained after the removal of basic and neutral fraction was a black mass which was similar to aniline black reported previously.

Separation of the basic fraction :

The basic fraction was chromatographed over alumina. Eluents were collected 25 ml each time.

From the petroleum ether eluent a solid compound mp 54° (0.1% yield) was obtained; ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 258, 270 (sh), 300 nm with log ϵ 3.9, 3.75, 3.54). This was found to be identical with diphenylene by direct comparison.

After the removal of diphenylene, another solid compound was obtained (3% yield) from the petroleum ether eluent which was crystallised from methanol, mp 65-66°; ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 244, 285 nm with log ϵ 7.80, 4.45). This was identified as 4-amino diphenylamine by direct comparison with authentic sample.

The petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) eluent furnished another crystalline compound (2% yield)

(i) Diphenylamine

(iii) Methyl diphenylamine

(v) $R_1 = CH_3; R_2 = H;$

(vii) $R_1 = CH_3; R_2 = R_3 = OCH_3$

(ii) Carbazole

(iv) $R_1 = CH_3; R_2 = R_3 = H$

(vi) $R_1 = CH_3; R_2 = H;$

(viii) $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = R_3 = OCH_3$

Several carbazoles (II, IV, VI, VIII) were synthesised by this method¹. The yield in the case of (II) and (IV) was satisfactory but it was not so with (VI) and (VIII). It was, therefore, of interest to examine the behaviour of aniline and related compounds under similar thermolysis reaction. We report here the results of these reactions.

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which was crystallised from alcohol, mp 126-127°; ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 295 nm with $\log \epsilon$ 4.28). The compound showed identical uv spectrum with the authentic sample of benzidine and showed no depression in mmp. with benzidine.

Another compound from benzene eluent was obtained (1% yield) which was identified as hydrazobenzene, mp 125° ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 250, 263, 295 nm with $\log \epsilon$ 4.4, 3.4, 3.5) by direct comparison with authentic sample.

Separation of the neutral fraction :

The neutral fraction was chromatographed over alumina. Eluents were collected 25 ml each time.

Petroleum ether eluent furnished a compound (5% yield) mp 56°; ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 240, 285 nm with $\log \epsilon$ 3.90, 4.23). It was identified as diphenylamine by direct comparison with authentic sample.

The petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) eluent furnished a solid compound (25% yield) mp 232°; ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 233, 257, 293 nm with $\log \epsilon$ 4.10, 4.18, 4.15). It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether and found to be carbazole by direct comparison with authentic sample.

Another compound (1% yield) mp 65° was obtained from the petroleum ether : benzene eluent ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}}$ 230, 312 nm with $\log \epsilon$ 3.39, 3.5). It was crystallised from alcohol and found to be identical with azobenzene.

Results and Discussion

It is evident that several products were isolated from the reaction mixture including ammonia. No iodinated product was, however, isolated. Carbazole(II), diphenylamine(I) and a black solid resembling aniline black were the major products isolated. Trace of azobenzene(X) was detected in the

neutral fraction. In the basic fraction 4-aminodiphenylamine(XI), benzidine(XII), diphenylamine(XIII) and hydrazobenzene(XIV) were identified by direct comparison and UV spectral measurements. Reaction was carried out with aniline without iodine as catalyst. No substantial changes were noted.

The earlier results on lead dioxide⁹ and peroxidase¹⁰ oxidations of aniline were explained on the basis of the radicals such as, (XV, XVI) leading to different products.

Recent studies on the anodic oxidation of aniline in aqueous acid gave product of emeraldine type¹¹ which was practically an octamer arising from the ionic species (XVII).

Anodic oxidation studies have further shown that aniline could undergo head to tail condensation¹² giving rise to benzidine(XII) and aminodiphenylamine(XI). In all these oxidative reactions the formation of diphenylamine or carbazole was not reported.

Iodine at high temperature has been conceived to give radical iodine which is hydrogen abstracting species. The generation of radical iodine(I) is essential for successive hydrogen abstraction. Under this hydrogen abstracting condition aniline may give rise to the following species (XVIII-XXI).

These species may couple to give the compounds (I, II, X, XI, XII, XIII, XIV). The formation of benzidine, aminodiphenylamine, hydrazobenzene and azobenzene, carbazole, diphenylamine could therefore be rationalised as follows.

Carbazole and diphenylamine have been found to be the major products in the I_2 catalysed thermal reaction of aniline. In the photolytic process the yield of N-methyl carbazole from N-methyl diphenylamine is more than the yield of carbazole from diphenylamine. In the anodic oxidation method involving diphenylamine, the yield is quite poor. The yield of carbazole from diphenylamine by thermal method has been found to be the best. In the thermal process, the formation of carbazole

from aniline could be conceived to go through diphenylamine which is known to cyclise to carbazole; The other mechanism as depicted from (XXII) to (II) cannot however be ruled out. The detection of ammonia in the reaction mixture stands in favour of this. Diphenylamine was obtained in small quantity when *p*-aminodiphenylamine was subjected to above thermal reaction. No derivative of carbazole was detected.

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